

The Stobbe Condensation. Part VI.* The Cyclisation of 3-Methoxycarbonyl-*cis*-4-methyl-4-phenyl and of 3-Methoxycarbonyl-*cis*-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-enoic Acid to the Corresponding Polysubstituted Naphthalene Derivatives

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3-Methoxycarbonyl-*cis*-4-methyl-4-phenyl- and 3-Methoxycarbonyl-*cis*-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-enoic acids (*cis*- β -half esters) are cyclised with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate into methyl 4-acetoxy-1-methyl- and 6-methoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoate which are converted into 1-methoxy-4-methyl- and 1,7-dimethoxy-4-methyl-naphthalene respectively.

Alcoholysis of *cis*- and *trans*-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-en-1,3-dicarboxylic anhydride yields α -methoxycarbonylmethyl-*trans*- and *cis*- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- β -methylacrylic acids (*cis*- and *trans*- α -half esters), respectively.

In the previous publication¹, it was proved that the Stobbe condensation of aromatic aldehydes with succinic acid esters yielded mainly the corresponding *cis*- β -half esters which were easily cyclised to the corresponding substituted naphthalenes. The aim of this investigation was to study the Stobbe condensation of acetophenones with methyl succinate in order to synthesise methyl-methoxy-substituted naphthalenes which are very difficult to prepare by the known methods, and at the same time to confirm or determine the configuration of the products.

Thus, heating acetophenone or *p*-methoxyacetophenone with methyl succinate in presence of potassium *tert*-butoxide¹ gave oily stereoisomeric mixtures of 3-methoxycarbonyl-*cis*-4-methyl-4-phenyl^{2,3} (*Ia* : R¹ = Me) and 3-methoxycarbonyl-*cis*-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-enoic acid (*Ib* : R¹ = Me), respectively; in about 70% yield. Crystallisation of the latter isomeric mixture of β -half ester (*Ib* : R¹ = Me) gave a small amount of 3-methoxycarbonyl-*cis*-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-enoic acid (*Ib* : R¹ = Me) as a crystalline solid, while the main product remained as uncrystallisable highly viscous oily mixture.

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Boiling the stereoisomeric mixture of β -half ester (Ia : $R^1 = \text{Me}$) with sodium acetate in acetic anhydride¹ effected the cyclisation of the *cis*- β -half ester (Ia : $R^1 = \text{Me}$) to the corresponding methyl 1-acetoxy-4-methyl-2-naphthoate (IIa : $R^1 = \text{Me}$, $R^2 = \text{OAc}$); similar cyclisation of the stereoisomeric mixture of β -half ester (Ib : $R^1 = \text{Me}$), gave the expected methyl 1-acetoxy-6-methoxy-4-methyl-2-naphthoate (IIb : $R^1 = \text{Me}$, $R^2 = \text{OAc}$).

Alkaline hydrolysis of the acetoxy-naphthoates (IIa and b : $R^1 = \text{Me}$, $R^2 = \text{OAc}$) gave 4-hydroxy-1-methyl- (IIa : $R^1 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = \text{OH}$) and 4-hydroxy-6-methoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoic acid (IIb : $R^1 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = \text{OH}$), respectively, and both gave the characteristic colour reaction for phenols (alc. FeCl_3). Both acids were converted by methyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in acetone into methyl 4-methoxy-1-methyl- (IIa : $R^1 = \text{Me}$, $R^2 = \text{OMe}$) and 4,6-dimethoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoate (IIb : $R^1 = \text{Me}$, $R^2 = \text{OMe}$) which on hydrolysis gave the corresponding naphthoic acids (IIa and b : $R^1 = \text{H}$, $R^2 = \text{OMe}$). Thence, decarboxylation with copper-bronze in quinoline gave 1-methyl-4-methoxy- and 4,6-dimethoxy-1-methyl-naphthalene, respectively. The former compound was obtained as an oil and therefore, it was identified as its mononitro-derivative^{1a}.

Hydrolysis of the crude stereoisomeric mixture (Ib : $R^1 = \text{Me}$) with boiling 15% aqueous-alcoholic (v/v) potassium hydroxide solution gave a mixture of acids from which *cis*-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-en-1,3-dicarboxylic acid (Ib : $R^1 = \text{H}$) was isolated by taking advantage of its very low solubility in benzene, and was identical with that obtained by a similar hydrolysis of the pure crystalline *cis*- β -half ester (Ib : $R^1 = \text{Me}$). The remaining acid mixture was fractionally crystallised from water, the isomeric *trans*-acid being the less soluble separated out first and thus leaving the *cis*-acid (Ib : $R^1 = \text{H}$) in the mother-liquor. Concentration followed by repeated crystallisation of the precipitated acid yielded the pure crystalline *cis*-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-en-1,3-dicarboxylic acid (Ib : $R^1 = \text{H}$).

The derived anhydrides of both the *cis*- and the *trans*- acids (Ib : $R^1 = \text{H}$) were converted with boiling methanol into α -methoxy-carbonylmethyl-*trans*- and *cis*- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- β -methyl-acrylic acid respectively, the former being different from the *cis*- β -half ester (Ib : $R^1 = \text{Me}$) obtained by the Stobbe condensation. The formation of these acrylic acid derivatives (α -half esters) by the alcoholysis of the corresponding anhydrides further supports the mechanism of their formation postulated by El-Assal and El-Abbady¹.

EXPERIMENTAL

Micronalyses were by Dr. A. Bernhardt, im Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Mülheim (Ruhr), Germany.

The Stobbe Condensation of Acetophenone with Dimethyl Succinate: Acetophenone (12 g., 1 mol.), methyl succinate (17.5 g., 1.2 mol.) in *tert.*-butanol (15 ml.), and potassium *tert.*-butoxide [from metallic potassium (5.8 g.) and the alcohol (85 ml.)] was treated as previously described¹. The product (*ca.* 16 g.) was extracted with boiling benzene, and the insoluble residue was filtered off. Evaporation of the solvent left the stereoisomeric mixture of 3-methoxycarbonyl-4-methyl-4-phenyl-3-enoic acid (Ia : R¹ = Me) as a viscous dark-brown oil^{2,3c} which was used as such in the following experiment.

Methyl 4-Acetoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoate (IIa : R¹ = Me, R² = OAc). The above crude stereoisomeric β -half ester (2.5 g.) was cyclised with sodium acetate (1.5 g.) in acetic anhydride (15 ml.) as usual¹. The oily product (*ca.* 2.7 g.) was then refluxed with methanol for 2 hr., alcohol evaporated and the residue was thoroughly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was successively washed with cold 15% sodium carbonate solution, with cold 2% sodium hydroxide solution, finally with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). The distillation of ether left a highly viscous oil which on crystallisation from methanol or benzene-light petroleum (b.p. 40–60°), gave *methyl-4-acetoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoate* in diagonal crystals, m.p. 76–77° (Found : C, 69.5; H, 5.3, OMe, 12.4. C₁₅H₁₄O₄ requires C, 69.7; H, 5.4, OMe, 12.1%).

4-Hydroxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoic Acid (IIa : R¹ = H, R² = OH) : The above acetoxy-naphthoate (0.8 g.) was hydrolysed with 15% aqueous-alcoholic (v/v) potassium hydroxide solution (15 ml.) (4 hour's refluxing) to give an acid, m.p. 200–202° (0.6 g.) which on crystallisation from acetone-benzene gave *4-hydroxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoic acid* in needles, m.p. 204–205° (Found : C, 71.5; H, 5.15. C₁₂H₁₀O₃ requires C, 71.3; H, 4.95%). This acid gave the characteristic colour reaction for phenols (alc. FeCl₃).

Methyl 4-Methoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoate (IIa : R¹ = Me, R² = OMe) : The preceding crude acid (2 g.), dimethyl sulphate (6.5 g.) and potassium carbonate (10 g.) in acetone (60 ml.) was treated in the usual manner¹. The product was crystallised from light-petroleum (b.p. 70–80°) to give *methyl 4-methoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoate* in clusters, m.p. 100–101° (Found : C, 73.3; H, 6.05; OMe, 26.45. C₁₄H₁₄O₃ requires C, 73.05; H, 6.1; 2 OMe, 26.95%). Hydrolysis of this latter methoxy-naphthoate (0.18 g.) as above gave *4-methoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoic acid* (from benzene) (0.15 g.), m.p. 161–162° (Found : C, 72.5; H, 5.75; OMe, 13.6. C₁₃H₁₂O₃ requires C, 72.2; H, 5.55; OMe, 14.35%).

4-Methoxy-1-methylnaphthalene : A solution of the above acid (0.2 g.) in quinoline (4 ml.) was heated to the boiling point with copper-bronze (0.1 g.) during 13 min., then an equal amount of copper-bronze was added portionwise to the boiling solution during 4 min., the whole was then refluxed for a further hour, and then worked up as usual¹. The product (*ca.* 0.12 g.) failed to give crystals even after its distillation in a vacuum at 150–160°/4 mm., followed by crystallisation in many organic solvents (Found : C, 83.5; H, 7.1; OMe, 18.5. C₁₂H₁₂O requires C, 83.7; H, 7; OMe, 18.0%). Therefore, the solution of this oily product

(ca. 0.12 g.) in acetic acid (1 ml.) was nitrated with a solution of nitric acid ($d = 1.42$) (0.15 ml.) in acetic acid (1 ml.) and the mixture was mechanically stirred at room temperature (20–25°) for 8 hr., and then at 60–70° (regulated water-bath) for 2 hr more. The reactants were poured into water and the product was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was thoroughly washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The distillation of ether left a residue which was repeatedly crystallised from light-petroleum (b.p. 30–50°) to give the mononitro-derivative of the above substituted naphthalene in brown fine crystals, m.p. 140–141° (Found : C, 66.2; H, 5.2; N, 6.25; OMe, 14.6. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 66.4; H, 5.1; N, 6.45; OMe, 14.3%).

3-Methoxycarbonyl-cis-4-(p-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-enoic Acid (Ib : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$) : *p*-Methoxyacetophenone (13.5 g., 1 ml.), dimethyl succinate (17.2, 1.2 mol.) in *tert.*-butanol (20 ml.), and potassium *tert.*-butoxide [from metallic potassium (5.8 g.) and the alcohol (80 ml.)] was treated as previously described¹. The product (ca. 18 g.) was extracted with boiling benzene and filtered from any insoluble product. Concentration of the benzene solution followed by dilution with light-petroleum (b.p. 40–60°) gave a crystalline product (ca. 1.2 g.). On repeated crystallisation from the same solvent or from methanol, it gave *3-methoxycarbonyl-cis-4-(p-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-enoic acid* in crystals with faint-yellowish tint, m.p. 102–103° (Found : C, 63.5; H, 6.0; OMe, 22.6. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 63.6; H, 6.1; 2 OMe, 23.5%). Evaporation of the original mother-liquor gave a highly viscous dark-brown oil which failed to give any further crystalline product from many suitable organic solvents.

Methyl 4-Acetoxy-6-methoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoate (IIb : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{OAc}$) : The above crude stereoisomeric mixture of β -half ester (Ib : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$) (17 g.) was cyclised with sodium acetate (6 g.) in acetic anhydride (85 ml.) as usual¹ (6 hours' refluxing). The product was thoroughly extracted with benzene, washed and dried (CaCl_2). Distillation of the solvent left a dark-brown highly viscous oil (ca. 18.5 g) which on treatment with ether, gave a light-brown solid which was filtered off, and then thoroughly washed with ether, m.p. 134–136° (ca. 5 g.). This solid product was refluxed with methanol (100 ml.) for 3 hr, alcohol evaporated, and the residue was re-extracted with benzene. The benzene solution was successively washed with cold 20% sodium carbonate solution, with cold 5% sodium hydroxide solution, finally with water and dried (CaCl_2). The distillation of the solvent left a solid residue which was crystallised from methanol to give *methyl 4-acetoxy-6-methoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoate* in yellow rhombic crystals, m.p. 141–142° (Found : C, 66.35; H, 5.7; OMe, 21.1. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 66.7; H, 5.55; 2 OMe, 21.5%).

When the pure crystalline *cis*- β -half ester (Ib : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$) was similarly cyclised, it gave the methoxy-naphthoate (IIb : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{OAc}$) with identical m.p. and mixed m.p. 141–142° (Found : C, 66.7; H, 5.4; OMe, 21.5%).

4-Hydroxy-6-methoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoic Acid (IIb : $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{OH}$) : Hydrolysis of the acetoxy-naphthoate (IIb : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{OAc}$) (1 g.) with 15% aqueous-alcoholic (v/v) potassium hydroxide solution (25 ml) (3 hours' refluxing) in the usual manner gave *4-hydroxy-6-methoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoic acid* (ca. 0.9 g.) in rhombic crystals (from acetone), m.p. 230–231° (Found : C, 67.2; H, 5.1; OMe, 13.5. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 67.2; H, 5.2; OMe,

13.4%). This acid was insoluble in either benzene or chloroform, but it gave the characteristic colour reaction for phenols (alc. FeCl_3).

Methyl 4,6-Dimethoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoate (IIb : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{OMe}$) : The above crude acid (0.9 g.) was treated with dimethyl sulphate (2.1 g.) and potassium carbonate (3.7 g.) in acetone (30 ml.) in the usual manner (2 hours' refluxing) to give the *methoxy-ester* (IIb : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{OMe}$) (ca. 0.9 g.) in fine needles with pinkish-tint, m.p. 88–89° (from benzene-light petroleum, b.p. 40–60°) (Found : C, 69.05; H, 6.2; OMe, 34.8. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 69.2; H, 6.15; 3 OMe, 35.1%). This ester (0.4 g.) was hydrolysed as above to *4,6-dimethoxy-1-methyl-2-naphthoic acid* (ca. 0.37 g.) in needles, m.p. 185–187° (from benzene) (Found : C, 68.1; H, 5.8; OMe, 25.2. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 68.3; H, 5.7; 2 OMe, 25.2%).

4,6-Dimethoxy-1-methylnaphthalene : A solution of the above methoxy acid (0.2 g.) in quinoline (4 ml.) was heated to the boiling point with copper-bronze (0.15 g.) during 30 min., then an equal amount of copper-bronze was added in portions to the boiling solution during 30 min., the whole was then refluxed for a further 30 min., and worked up as usual. The product (ca. 0.1 g.) was crystallised from light-petroleum (b.p. 60–70°) to give *4,6-dimethoxy-1-methylnaphthalene*, m.p. 55–56° (Found : C, 77.4; H, 6.7; OMe, 29.5. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.2; H, 6.9; 2 OMe, 30.7%).

Hydrolysis of the Stereoisomeric β -Half Ester (Ib : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$) : The crude oily stereoisomeric β -half ester (Ib : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$) (ca. 8 g.) was hydrolysed as above (4 hours' refluxing). Acidification of the clear alkaline solution (charcoal) precipitated a mixture of acid product (ca. 7 g.), m.p. 125–132° and which was separated into its components as follows : a) the dry acid mixture (ca. 1.8 g.) was treated with boiling benzene and the insoluble product (ca. 0.5 g.) was filtered off and crystallised from acetone-benzene to give *cis-4-(p-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-en-1,3-dicarboxylic acid* in plates, m.p. 188–189°, undepressed on admixture with a specimen prepared by the hydrolysis of the pure *cis- β -half ester* (Ib : $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$) (Found : C, 62.7; H, 5.7; OMe, 12.0. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 62.4; H, 5.6; OMe, 12.4%). Concentration of the original benzene solution gave a crystalline product, m.p. 135–137° (ca. 0.8 g.) which on repeated crystallisation from water, gave *trans-4-(p-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-en-1,3-dicarboxylic acid* in shining plates, m.p. 141–142° (gas evolution), depressed on admixture with the above *cis*-isomer (Found : C, 62.0; H, 5.7; OMe, 12.0%). b) the acid mixture (2 g.) was fractionally crystallised from water, the first crop gave after repeated crystallisation from the same solvent, the *cis*-acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 188–189°. The second fraction gave after repeated crystallisation from water, the *trans*-acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 141–142° (gas evolution). c) the acid mixture (1.4 g.) (obtained from aqueous mother liquor) was thoroughly dried and then treated with acetyl chloride (10 ml.) and left for 2 days at room-temperature (20–25°)^{3a,e}. Evaporation of the acetyl chloride at reduced pressure left a highly viscous oil which was dissolved in ether. The ethereal solution was extracted with cold 2% sodium hydroxide solution, followed by 3% sodium carbonate solution, and finally dried (Na_2SO_4). Acidification of the sodium hydroxide extract precipitated an acid product which after crystallisation from acetone-benzene gave the above *cis*-acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 188–189°. Evaporation of ether left a residue which was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum (b.p. 30–50°) to give *trans-4-(p-methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-en-1,3-dicarboxylic anhydride*, m.p. and mixed m.p. 82–83° (see below).

cis-4-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-en-1,3-dicarboxylic Anhydride : The above *cis*-acid (1 g.) was boiled with acetyl chloride (5 ml.) for 4 hr. After evaporation, the *anhydride* formed plates (ca. 1.8 g.), m.p. 142–143° (from benzene) (Found : C, 67.3; H, 5.1; OMe, 12.9. C₁₃H₁₂O₄ requires C, 67.25; H, 5.2; OMe, 13.3%).

α -Methoxycarbonylmethyl-trans- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- β -methyl-acrylic Acid : The above *cis*-anhydride (0.2 g.) was refluxed with absolute methanol (10 ml.) for 5 hr. Evaporation followed by crystallisation of the residue (0.19 g.) from benzene-light petroleum (b.p. 70–80°) gave α -methoxycarbonylmethyl-trans- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- β -methyl-acrylic acid in needles, m.p. 123–124°, depressed on admixture with a specimen of its isomeric *cis*- β -half ester (Ib : R¹ = Me) (Found : C, 63.85; H, 6.1; OMe, 22.5. C₁₄H₁₆O₅ requires C, 63.6; H, 6.1; 2 OMe, 23.5%).

trans-4-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-4-methyl-3-en-1,3-dicarboxylic Anhydride : The above *trans*-acid (0.2 g.) with acetyl chloride (3 ml.) (3 hours' refluxing) gave its *trans*-anhydride (from benzene-light petroleum, b.p. 30–50°) in needles, m.p. 82–83°, depressed on admixture with a specimen of its isomeric *cis*-anhydride (Found : C, 66.9; H, 5.3, OMe, 12.8%).

α -Methoxycarbonylmethyl-*cis*- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- β -methyl-acrylic Acid : The above *trans*-anhydride (0.2 g.) in absolute methanol gave as in the preceding case α -methoxycarbonylmethyl-*cis*- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)- β -methyl-acrylic acid (ca. 1.9 g.) in needles (from benzene), m.p. 102–103°, depressed on admixture with a specimen of either the above *trans*- α -half ester or its isomeric *cis*- β -half ester obtained by the Stobbe condensation (Found : C, 63.4; H, 5.9; OMe, 22.4%).

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